

Legal Policy Recommendations for Enhancing the Effectiveness of State Management in Real Estate Business: A Case Study of the Real Estate Market in Vietnam

Tran Thi Bich Nga ¹, Bui Huy Tung ², Nguyen Thi Viet Huong ³ and Vo Song Toan ^{4*}

¹ Lecturer, Faculty of Economic Law, Ho Chi Minh University of Banking, 84, Vietnam
E-mail: ngatb@hub.edu.vn; <https://orcid.org/0009-0006-0299-1700>

² Lecturer, Faculty of Economic Law, Ho Chi Minh University of Banking, 84, Vietnam
E-mail: tungbh@hub.edu.vn; <https://orcid.org/0009-0008-8704-5741>

³ Lecturer, Institute of State and Law, Vietnam Academy of Social Sciences, 84, Vietnam
E-mail: nguyenviethuong198@gmail.com; <https://orcid.org/0009-0000-2386-7879>

⁴ Vice Dean, Faculty of Economic Law, Ho Chi Minh University of Banking, 84, Vietnam
*Corresponding author e-mail: toanvs@hub.edu.vn; <https://orcid.org/0009-0006-5268-9331>

Abstract

Background: The real estate market is considered one of the pillars of the economy, helping to concentrate resources and create fixed assets for the country. The development of the real estate market creates growth momentum for related industries.

Objective: This study analysed the factors influencing the effectiveness of State management in the real estate business. The authors then proposed legal policy recommendations for enhancing the effectiveness of state management in the real estate business in Vietnam.

Methodology: The study used a descriptive survey design, while copies of the questionnaire were distributed through online platforms to the respondents, who include economic experts, state management officials, and real estate businesses. The convenience sample of 655 respondents was used to test the model's fit and hypotheses, utilising structural equation modelling to assess the factors impacting the effectiveness of state management.

Results: The results indicate that the legal framework, management capacity, information transparency, technology application, and credit policy have a significant impact on the effectiveness of state management.

Conclusion: It is essential to consider the legal framework, management capacity, information transparency, technology application, and credit policy when considering ways to improve the real estate industry.

Unique Contribution: These results offer practical insights for developing legal policy recommendations to enhance the effectiveness of state management in the real estate market in Vietnam.

Key Recommendation: The government should ensure unified management at both the central and local levels of the real estate market by developing financial support packages to reduce home loan interest rates, particularly for low-income groups, thereby facilitating quicker access to housing.

Keywords: Effectiveness, state management, real estate business, legal policy recommendations

Introduction

The real estate market is crucial to the national economy, as it helps meet people's housing needs, supports urban development, and contributes to tourism, among other sectors. Studies conducted on a global scale have shown that problems in the financial, monetary, and real estate markets are common causes of economic crises (Simons et al., 2023). The stagnant real estate market is leading to stagnation in many other markets. Furthermore, rising land prices are making it difficult for people, especially low-income families, to access housing. Increasing land prices and speculation have also contributed to higher housing costs, creating an imbalance between supply and demand, particularly in large urban areas (Adade et al., 2022). Moreover, the virtual land fever in suburban areas has pushed land prices too high, beyond people's ability to pay, increasing the risk of forming a real estate bubble. This can cause severe economic and societal consequences if not controlled and handled promptly.

The real estate market recorded positive signals; it is still not out of trouble, and the recovery is uneven across market segments. The problematic situation in the real estate market continues to last until now, mainly due to the many legal problems in the real estate market (Febriyanti et al., 2024), precisely: (1) Planning problems: The development of real estate projects in some localities is not following planning and plans, not suitable for market needs. In cases where detailed planning has been approved but is unsuitable for higher-level planning, the legal basis has expired. (2) Investment problems: The procedures for investing in real estate projects are regulated in many legal documents and are carried out through many steps, so the time to carry out investment procedures is long. Problems in allowing adjustments to project progress for objective cases. (3) Transaction problems: The regulation that real estate transactions are not required through the floor has created a legal gap - this is the basis for the formation of ghost projects and customer fraud cases. (4) Information problems: Updating information about the real estate market is still difficult and does not meet practical needs, causing many shortcomings in the operation and management of the real estate market and causing losses to the state budget. Therefore, the study's objectives are to analyse the factors influencing the effectiveness of state management and provide legal policy recommendations enhancing the effectiveness of state management in the real estate business of the real estate market in Vietnam.

Literature Review

The effectiveness of state management

Ultimately, the actions of subjects of state administrative management, including public officials, concerning the use of resources like money, time, and labour determine the efficiency of state management (Breuer & Steininger, 2020). Indicators of growth that keep things stable and progressing take a wide range of interrelationships into account, including those between the State and its citizens, the efficiency of social services, the priority given to short-term vs. long-term objectives, the interests of the Federal Government and those of individual municipalities, and many more (Rattanaprichavej, 2023). State administrative agencies and public service performers' activities related to the executive and executive functions, as outlined in the Law, are the foundation of effective state management.

Real estate business

Real estate business is the investment of large amounts of capital to carry out construction, purchase, transfer, and receive transfers for sale; provide real estate brokerage services; lease, sublease, or lease-purchase real estate; provide real estate consulting services or real estate management for profit purposes (Schütt, 2021). Trading in this type of product must comply with the following legal principles: (1) Equality before the Law; freedom to negotiate based on respecting the rights and legitimate interests of the parties under the contract without violating the provisions of the Law (Deakin, 2023). (2) Real estate

put into business must fully satisfy the conditions prescribed by this Law. (3) Organisations and individuals are entitled to conduct real estate business in areas outside the national defence and security protection area, according to planning and land use plans approved by competent state agencies.

Real estate market

Currently, there are many different views on the concept of the real estate market. Let's look at other opinions on this market: (1) The real estate market is also called the land market because all houses or structures built on land are called real estate (Bağış et al., 2024). The land itself is real estate, creating many other real estate types. (2) The real estate market is the activity of exchanging, buying, selling, leasing, or mortgaging the right to use real estate according to the market rules under the management of the State (Febriyanti et al., 2024). All exchanging, buying, and selling land activities must be based on relevant laws. This concept has reflected all the actual activities of the real estate market. It helps people easily recognize the scope and content of the market. (3) The real estate market is where real estate trading activities occur and is a space for buyers and sellers to interact, negotiate, and agree on prices (Shaw, 2020). Not only that, the real estate market is also a system of relationships where transactions are conducted between parties.

Theoretical framework and hypothesis development

Many internal and external elements, direct and indirect, primary and secondary, influence the efficacy of state management in the real estate sector. Various criteria have been used to classify these factors (Chawla & Kumar, 2022). The 5 main factors that affect state management's effectiveness in the real estate business sector. Five key factors influencing the effectiveness of state management include legal framework, management capacity, information transparency, technology application, and credit policy (Kavaarpuo et al., 2023; Bang & Kwon, 2022). Therefore, improving the efficiency of state management is one of the top key tasks, and is also the process of building a clean, capable, and gradually modernised administration system to effectively and efficiently manage the work of the State, promote healthy and correct social development, and serve the people.

The relationship between the legal framework and the effectiveness of state management

The legal framework has a significant positive impact on the effectiveness of state management in the real estate business sector. Clear and comprehensive legal regulations help define roles and responsibilities, minimize conflict, and ensure compliance (Li & Chau, 2019). Transparency and fairness in legal regulations build trust and promote effective decision-making. A flexible legal framework allows for quick adaptation to market changes, such as the emergence of new real estate types (Deakin, 2023). Strong enforcement mechanisms help prevent violations and enhance the reputation of regulators. Reality shows that a strong legal system brings stability to the market, enhances investor confidence, and minimizes disputes. Continuous improvement of the legal framework is essential for improving state management efficiency. Based on this, the authors proposed H1 in Figure 1.

The relationship between management capacity and the effectiveness of state management

Management capacity positively correlates with state management effectiveness in the real estate business. When management capacity is improved, authorities enforce the Law more effectively, reduce violations, and create a transparent business environment (Bang & Kwon, 2022). A team of highly qualified staff helps make timely and practical decisions. The application of modern technology, such as artificial intelligence (AI) and big data, optimises market monitoring and forecasting. Good management capacity also enhances confidence from investors and people, promoting cooperation between stakeholders (Bağış et al., 2024; Brill & Robin, 2020) and proposed H2 in Figure 1.

The relationship between the transparency of information and the effectiveness of state management

Information transparency positively correlates with state management effectiveness in the real estate business. When legal, planning, and price information is clearly publicised, investors and people can easily make accurate decisions, minimising the risk of disputes and speculation (Shaarawy et al., 2024). Regulators also benefit from the ability to monitor and control the market more effectively. The digital system and national real estate database ensure information is updated, transparent, and accessible (Tan & Miller, 2023; Shaw, 2020). This not only enhances fairness in the market but also creates healthy competition. The following hypothesis is proposed for H3 in Figure 1.

The relationship between the application of technology and the effectiveness of state management

Technology application has a positive relationship with state management efficiency in the real estate business, helping to optimise the market monitoring and management process (Mu & Antwi-Afari, 2023). Modern technology, such as artificial intelligence, big data, and Blockchain, provides powerful tools to manage real estate information transparently, accurately, and quickly. The online management system helps shorten the time to process administrative procedures and improve the efficiency of public services (Adedigba et al., 2024). At the same time, technology supports market trend forecasting, helping management agencies make timely and effective decisions and proposing H4 in Figure 1.

The relationship between credit policies and the effectiveness of state management

Credit policy has a positive relationship with state management effectiveness in the real estate business, playing an essential role in regulating the market and ensuring financial stability. When appropriately designed, credit policies help control capital flows into real estate, limit speculation, and prevent market bubbles (Starr et al., 2021). Simultaneously, preferential lending promotes sustainable development by encouraging investments in green real estate and social housing. Credit risks are mitigated, and governmental agencies' financial management skills are enhanced by stringent monitoring of loan capital (Kavaarpuo et al., 2023). Real estate market management can be more efficient with open and equitable credit regulations, inspiring trust among investors and the general public (Adade et al., 2022). Effective state administration, stable market development, and the planned H5 in Figure 1 depend on well-managed credit regulations.

Based on the analysis of related domestic and foreign studies, the authors propose a research model in which these elements work in tandem, managerial efficiency rises, and the real estate market stays the same.

Source: Proposal of the authors

Figure 1: Conceptual model for five factors influencing the effectiveness of state management

Figure 1 shows that there are five factors influencing the effectiveness of state management, including: (1) Legal framework (LF), (2) Management capacity (MC), (3) Information transparency (IT), (4) Technology application (TA), and (5) Credit policy (CP).

Research Methods

The research process, through two phases, qualitative and quantitative, helps ensure that the research results have a solid scientific basis. The qualitative phase identifies initial factors, while the quantitative phase tests and evaluates the impact level, providing realistic and appropriate policy recommendations.

Phase 1: Qualitative research

The qualitative phase is carried out to identify the initial factors affecting the effectiveness of state management in the real estate business and build a scientific basis for the quantitative phase. The main activity in this phase is to interview 30 real estate business experts in 5 major cities of Vietnam, including Hanoi, Ho Chi Minh City, Da Nang, Hai Phong, and Can Tho City. Experience and familiarity with the local real estate market are the deciding factors in the expert selection process. Topics covered in the interviews included suggestions for developing suitable measurement scales, judgments on the factors impacting the efficacy of state management, and the level of influence of each element.

Each expert interview lasts thirty to sixty minutes and can be held in person or over the Internet. The interview data were coded and evaluated to identify the most critical aspects. The set of preliminary scales that are the end product of the qualitative phase makes establishing a survey and continuing testing in the quantitative phase possible.

Phase 2: Quantitative research

Step 1: Based on the findings of the qualitative phase, the authors created a survey table to measure the various aspects influencing the effectiveness of state management in the real estate company. The survey uses a 5-point Likert scale for all measurement items to maintain objectivity and clarity. Before its formal

deployment, the survey was pilot-tested to assess its clarity and rationality. The survey is carried out online through several media, reaching a diverse audience on a large scale (Hair et al., 2018).

Step 2: The authors gathered data from 700 respondents in six central Southeast provinces and cities, including Ho Chi Minh City. Ho Chi Minh, Dong Nai, Binh Duong, Ba Ria-Vung Tau, Tay Ninh, and Binh Phuoc. The survey respondents included 200 real estate managers, 200 brokers, 200 investors, 50 economic experts with real estate knowledge, and 50 real estate lecturers. Each target group is selected according to proper criteria, ensuring the survey sample is representative and diverse (Hair et al., 2018).

Step 3: The authors undertake a preliminary analysis and check the data. After data collection is complete, it is reviewed for any irregularities that could indicate fraud or missing information. Before performing an in-depth analysis with 655 respondents providing correct answers, the data is cleaned using analytical tools like SPSS or Excel to ensure it is comprehensive and accurate.

Step 4: Analyze data: Data analysis is performed using SPSS or AMOS software with methods such as checking the reliability of the scale using Cronbach's Alpha (>0.6), exploratory factor analysis (EFA) to evaluate the scales' appropriateness, using the KMO test ($0.5 \leq KMO \leq 1$) and Bartlett's Test of Sphericity (Sig. < 0.05), confirmatory factor analysis (CFA) also examines the links between observable variables and latent components. Assess model fit using the Chi-square (χ^2) indices to determine goodness-of-fit. It should be non-significant ($p > 0.05$). Comparative Fit Index - CFI ≥ 0.90 indicates a strong fit. Tucker-Lewis Index - TLI ≥ 0.90 indicates a good fit. An RMSEA of < 0.08 marks a reasonable match. The SRMR < 0.08 is ideal. The analysis helps identify the most critical factors and their influence on state management effectiveness.

Step 5: Conclusion and recommendations: From the analysis results, the study synthesises the main findings and draws conclusions about factors affecting the effectiveness of state management in the real estate business. Based on these findings, the study proposes policy implications to improve the legal framework, enhance management capacity, make information transparent, apply technology, and optimise credit policy to promote sustainable real estate market development.

Study Results

Descriptive statistics and testing the reliability of the scale

The survey sample included 655 respondents, most female (59.2%) and most married (62.1%). Respondents are concentrated in the 35-40 age group (30.7%) and mainly have income from 15 to less than 20 million VND/month (31.0%). The most common working time is from 10 to under 15 years (30.7%), followed by the group from 15 to under 20 years (30.5%). The data shows that the survey sample is diverse, reflecting the characteristics of the real estate market. This is suitable for analyzing factors affecting this field.

Testing the reliability of the scale

We checked the measurement scales' reliability to make sure they accurately assessed the theoretical study model's constructs. Table 1 displays the outcomes.

Table 1: Testing scale reliability for five factors affecting the effectiveness of state management

Code	Initial variable	Mean	Standard Deviation	Cronbach's alpha
------	------------------	------	--------------------	------------------

LF:	LF1, LF2, LF3, LF 4	3.048	0.982	0.950
MC:	MC1, MC2, MC3, MC4	3.405	0.904	0.849
IT:	IT1, IT2, IT3, IT4	2.377	0.683	0.868
TA:	TA1, TA2, TA3, TA4	3.087	0.992	0.951
CP:	CP1, CP2, CP3, CP4	3.038	0.981	0.941
ESM:	ESM1, ESM2, ESM3	3.349	0.967	0.939

Source: Data analysis results of the authors

Table 1 reveals that all Cronbach's Alpha values above 0.7 indicate strong reliability of the scales on factors impacting state management in real estate companies. The legal framework (LF) and technology application (TA) scales had high Cronbach's Alphas of 0.950 and 0.951, indicating excellent response uniformity. Management capacity (MC), information transparency (IT), and credit policy (CP) scales have Cronbach's Alpha values from 0.849 to 0.941 and are reliable. The efficiency of state management (ESM) scale scored 0.939 on Cronbach's Alpha, indicating good measurement quality. The information transparency (IT) scale scored 2.377, indicating that this area requires development, while most aspects scored above 3.0. This verifies the measuring scales' viability for further study and stresses the necessity for transparency to increase state management efficiency.

Exploratory factor analysis and confirmatory factor analysis

The overall goodness-of-fit indices include: Chi-Square/df = 2.630 < 3.0; GFI = 0.937 > 0.9; CFI = 0.975 > 0.9; TLI = 0.969 > 0.9; RMSEA = 0.050 < 0.8, indicating that the model meets the required analytical standards. After conducting a series of analyses, the model results are presented in Figure 2.

Source: Data analysis results of the authors

Figure 2: SEM results for five factors influencing the effectiveness of state management

Figure 2 shows that SEM analysis shows that legal framework (LF), management capacity (MC), information transparency (IT), technology application (TA), and credit policy (CP) all positively and significantly affect state management (ESM) in the real estate sector. The legal framework (LF) has the most significant impact, underlining the importance of a strong legal system. Innovation and good governance also affect technology application (TA) and management capability (MC). Information transparency (IT) indirectly improves decision-making and reduces risk. CFI, TLI, and RMSEA indicators met the criteria, demonstrating the reliability of the SEM model. The above factors must be fully improved to strengthen state administration in the real estate sector.

Table 2: Testing for factors influencing the effectiveness of state management

Relationship			Standardized Estimate	SE	C.R	<i>p</i>	Results
MC	→	ESM	0.185	0.037	5.063	***	Accepted H2
IT	→	ESM	0.082	0.064	2.896	0.004	Accepted H3
TA	→	ESM	0.517	0.033	14.514	***	Accepted H4
CP	→	ESM	0.130	0.032	3.969	***	Accepted H5
LF	→	ESM	0.107	0.028	3.286	0.001	Accepted H1

Source: Results from the data analysis by the authors; Note: *** $p < 0.01$.

Table 2 demonstrates that all five criteria have a positive and significant impact on effective state management. Technology application (TA) has the most significant influence, with a coefficient of 0.517, indicating that technological innovation improves management. Management capability (MC) and credit policy (CP) exhibit substantial effects with coefficients of 0.185 and 0.130, respectively, stressing sound governance and financial policies. Information transparency (IT) and legal framework (LF) also positively affect, with coefficients of 0.082 and 0.107, respectively. This shows that technology innovation, management capacity, and policy perfection are needed to improve state administration in the real estate sector.

Discussion of Findings

By shedding light on the role of technology implementation, the study makes numerous novel additions to our theoretical and practical knowledge of real estate industry state management:

Technology application (TA) ranks highest in influencing ESM effectiveness, according to the statistics based on a standardised coefficient of 0.517. This highlights the significance of state-of-the-art innovations such as AI, Big Data, and Blockchain in improving market management and oversight (Li & Chau, 2019; Deakin, 2023; Rattanaprichavej, 2023). As a result, public administration can only progress by investing in technology. The development of modern technology brings clear competitive advantages to businesses that take the lead in applying technology. Today, real estate businesses can increase operational efficiency by implementing digital technologies such as process automation, providing customers with fast and convenient search and payment experiences.

According to Bang and Kwon (2022) and Bağış et al. (2024), the research is built and evaluated using five pillars: legitimate framework (LF), management competency (MC), information transparency (IT), technology application (TA), and credit policy (CP). According to the results, each factor influences management effectiveness, albeit to varying degrees. A novel approach to measuring state management's efficacy has emerged through quantitative and categorical methods.

This study contributes to the expanding literature on state management by highlighting the real estate industry, which stands out due to its specific features and sizeable economic impact and paying great attention to the housing market. Public management research in Vietnam is lacking in this realm (Tan & Miller, 2023; Shaarawy et al., 2024). Additionally, the research used both quantitative and qualitative methods concurrently. Using a combination of quantitative (SEM) and qualitative (expert surveys) methodologies, this study builds the measuring scale and identifies its components. Because of this integration, the research findings are specific to be accurate and reliable (Adedigba et al., 2024).

Policy factors that matter with practical implications. The study's findings can inform practical policy recommendations to strengthen the legal framework governing the real estate market, enhance managerial capabilities, and stimulate technological innovation for sustainable development. These new findings improve the research's scientific value, and legislators may utilise this information to craft and implement more effective state management strategies (Kavaarpuo et al., 2023; Bang & Kwon, 2022).

Conclusion and Recommendations

To identify the elements impacting the efficacy of state management, we used structural equation modelling to evaluate the model's fit and hypotheses with a convenience sample of 655 respondents. Based on their standardised estimations, the analysis pinpoints the most critical aspects impacting the effectiveness of state management (ESM) in the real estate industry. With a normalised estimate of 0.517, technology application (TA) is ranked top, indicating its substantial influence on enhancing management processes. The importance of financial and governance regulations is emphasised by placing management capacity (MC) second and credit policy (CP) third, with estimations of 0.185 and 0.130, respectively. Estimates for information transparency (IT) and legal framework (LF) are 0.082 and 0.107, respectively, suggesting that they are secondary concerns. These results establish a definitive hierarchy for prioritising enhancements in state management. Based on the results, the authors offer the following policy recommendations for enhancing the efficacy of state management.

(1) Improving technology application (TA): Modernising real estate state administration requires a quantum leap in technological proficiency. Machine learning (ML), big data, and Blockchain are cutting-edge technologies that can improve market transparency and operational efficiency. Technology that can manage real-time property data is essential for effectively monitoring and enforcing property rights. The application of predictive analytics allows for the reduction of risks and the anticipation of trends. The digitisation of financial transactions and paperwork will reduce opportunities for fraud, waste, and corruption. Consistent technological tools across regions, combined with public-private partnerships, can drive innovative solutions. Ongoing education is necessary to enhance the technical competence of government employees. Protecting private information and using automated mechanisms to detect and punish breaches should be our top cybersecurity priority.

(2) Improving management capacity (MC): Increasing management capability is essential for the effective administration of the real estate business. The primary objectives of any all-inclusive training program should be conflict management, strategic decision-making, and regulatory oversight. Central and local governments should establish collaborative channels to improve effort coordination. Allocating enough resources allows operations to run smoothly and provides performance evaluation methodologies to quantify effective management teams. Government officials may keep up with the latest advancements in their sector by routinely participating in knowledge-sharing events like seminars and conferences. Administrative processes will be streamlined and bureaucratic red tape reduced, allowing operations to run more efficiently. Specialised task groups take on challenging problems, and decision-making

transparency builds trust among stakeholders by enhancing communication between departments and governance to coordinate our activities better.

(3) Improving credit policy (CP): Lending policy optimisation is critical for fostering the housing market's long-term growth. Policymakers should prioritize funding, including interest rates, for environmentally friendly and affordable housing projects. Reining in speculative funding requires strict restrictions for the sake of responsible investing and volatility reduction. Jointly developing transparent lending systems with financial institutions can improve accessibility for all stakeholders. Reviewing policies frequently might help you stay relevant and respond to changes in the industry. Explicit criteria for loan approval might lead to less red tape and higher productivity. Educating stakeholders through financial literacy efforts can help them better understand the concept of responsible borrowing. A centralised monitoring system can keep tabs on credit performance, and risk assessment frameworks can ensure that credit-backed initiatives are feasible.

(4) Improving legal framework (LF): A robust legislative framework is necessary for the State to oversee the real estate sector successfully. It is essential to harmonise laws such as the Land and Housing Law to provide uniformity and streamline administrative processes. Punitive measures, such as fines, must be implemented to ensure compliance. Legislative provisions must be continuously updated to keep up with the ever-changing market and technological changes. It is possible to increase compliance with real estate regulations through public education campaigns. The formation of specialist legal organisations to manage disputes would be more cost-effective. When various locations adopt uniform regulatory norms, inconsistencies will diminish. Ensuring that regulations are inclusive and practical requires stakeholder participation in the legislative process.

(5) Improving information transparency (IT): More transparency in the real estate industry's data can go a long way toward fostering responsibility and confidence. Establishing a nationwide database that provides current information on property ownership, transactions, and planning would be beneficial. Updating and making digital platforms available regularly will ensure complete and trustworthy data. Developers and brokers who fail to disclose accurate project information need accountability. Partnerships between the public and private sectors have the potential to increase the reliability and quality of data while also making platforms accessible to all stakeholders via intuitive user interfaces. It is essential to standardize data collection processes across regions to ensure uniformity.

Limitations and future research: The generalizability of this study to other places may be limited due to its concentration on a confined sample in Vietnam. Policymakers and end-users, who are underrepresented, provide a narrow perspective. Also, it doesn't consider how technology revolutions and economic fluctuations impact state management, which are examples of dynamic market dynamics. Moving forward, research should look into barriers to technology adoption, include a broader range of stakeholders, and cover more ground geographically. To further enhance the effectiveness of state management, longitudinal studies and comparisons across sectors might yield significant insights.

References

Adade, D., Kuusaana, E. D., Timo de Vries, W., & Gavu, E. K. (2022). Housing finance strategies for low-income households in secondary cities: Contextualization under customary tenure in Ghana. *Housing Policy Debate*, 32(3), 549-572. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10511482.2021.1905026>.

- Adedigba, M. I., Adeniran, A. O., & Familusi, O. B. (2024). Technologies in real estate development: A review. *Systemic Analytics*, 2(2), 279-290. <https://doi.org/10.31181/sa22202429>.
- Bağış, M., Altınay, L., & Saygılı, M. (2024). Regulatory institutions, dynamic managerial capabilities, and strategic entrepreneurial performance. *Journal of Small Business and Enterprise Development*, 31(6), 1249-1276. <https://doi.org/10.1108/JSBED-01-2024-0016>.
- Bang, D. W., & Kwon, H. (2022). Policy impact analysis of housing policies using housing cycles. *Sage Open*, 12(3), 1-14. <https://doi.org/10.1177/21582440221113844>.
- Breuer, W., & Steininger, B. I. (2020). Recent trends in real estate research: A comparison of recent working papers and publications using machine learning algorithms. *Journal of Business Economics*, 90(7), 963-974. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11573-020-01005-w>.
- Brill, F., & Robin, E. (2020). The risky business of real estate developers: Network building and risk mitigation in London and Johannesburg. *Urban Geography*, 41(1), 36-54. <https://doi.org/10.1080/02723638.2019.1637211>.
- Chawla, N., & Kumar, B. (2022). Does Indian real estate regulation protect urban homebuyers? policy implications. *Cogent Business & Management*, 9(1), 1-27. <https://doi.org/10.1080/23311975.2022.2117164>.
- Deakin, S. (2023). The legal construction of management: A neo-realist framing and genealogical case study. *Journal of Corporate Law Studies*, 23(2), 375-396. <https://doi.org/10.1080/14735970.2024.2309739>.
- Febriyanti, D., Widianingsih, I., Sumaryana, A., & Buchari, R. A. (2024). The typology and determinant of performance measurement for public sector organizations – a literature review. *Cogent Business & Management*, 11(1), 1-20. <https://doi.org/10.1080/23311975.2024.2315681>.
- Hair, J., Anderson, R., Tatham, R., Black, W. (2018). *Multivariate data analysis*. US: Prentice-Hall: Upper Saddle River, NJ, USA.
- Kavaarpuo, G., Mintah, K., & Donkor-Hyiaman, K. A. (2023). Financing housing development in an underdeveloped financial market: Learning from developers' financing adaptations?. *Housing Policy Debate*, 34(6), 918-945. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10511482.2023.2237004>.
- Li, L., & Chau, K. W. (2019). What motivates a developer to sell before completion?. *The Journal of Real Estate Finance and Economics*, 59(2), 209-232. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11146-018-9662-3>.
- Mu, X., & Antwi-Afari, M. F. (2023). The applications of Internet of things (IoT) in industrial management: A science mapping review. *International Journal of Production Research*, 62(5), 1928-1952. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00207543.2023.2290229>.
- Rattanaprichavej, N. (2023). Decision-making process towards real estate agents, landlords, and expatriate tenants' criteria with perspective from principal-agent theory. *Cogent Business & Management*, 10(3), 1-22. <https://doi.org/10.1080/23311975.2023.2288692>.
- Schütt, M. (2021). Systematic variation in waste site effects on residential property values: A meta-regression analysis and benefit transfer. *Environmental and Resource Economics*, 78(3), 381-416. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10640-021-00536-2>.
- Shaarawy, E. B., Abdel-Latif, M. M., & Salheen, M. A. (2024). Understanding the implications of successive waves of currency devaluation and associated government reforms for real estate market. *HBRC Journal*, 20(1), 275-299. <https://doi.org/10.1080/16874048.2024.2310457>.
- Shaw, J. (2020). Platform real estate: Theory and practice of new urban real estate markets. *Urban Geography*, 41(8), 1037-1064. <https://doi.org/10.1080/02723638.2018.1524653>.
- Simons, R., Karam, A., Xiao, Y., & Caldwell, A. S. (2023). Research and citation trends in sustainable real estate. *Journal of Real Estate Literature*, 31(1), 48-66. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09277544.2023.2186725>.
- Starr, C. W., Saginor, J., & Worzala, E. (2021). The rise of PropTech: Emerging industrial technologies and their impact on real estate. *Journal of Property Investment & Finance*, 39(2), 157-169. <https://doi.org/10.1108/JPIF-08-2020-0090>.
- Tan, Z., & Miller, N. G. (2023). Connecting digitalization and sustainability: Proptech in the real estate operations and management. *Journal of Sustainable Real Estate*, 15(1), 1-14. <https://doi.org/10.1080/19498276.2023.2203292>.